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GGG Wave 1 Belgium: Item non-response

Christophe Vandeschrick, Jean-Paul Sanderson

GGG

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GGS Wave 1 Belgium:
Item non-response

Christophe Vandeschrick

Jean-Paul Sanderson

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1 Preface

Changing families and populations are presenting growing challenges for industrialized societies. As a result of low fertility levels prevailing for a long time, many countries are now expected to face labour shortages simultaneously with the demand to support a rapidly growing number of retired persons (UNECE, 2008). At the same time, younger generations tend to postpone marriage and parenting. Increased prevalence of consensual unions, decreasing stability of co-residential partnerships and the emergence of non-residential partnerships are other trends that can be seen in many countries (UNECE, 2008). Multifaceted family change requires that governments and other social partners monitor and, when necessary, step in to help families preserve and strengthen the ties that bind their members. To successfully meet these and other challenges, the UNECE Population Activity Unit launched the Generations & Gender Programme (GGP) to equip policy makers with a better understanding of the causes underlying recent developments and their consequences, with particular attention given to the relationships between children and parents (generations) and between partners (gender).

The GGP has two main pillars. The first is the system of national Generations & Gender Surveys (GGS), which are panel surveys of a representative sample of the 18 to 79 year-old resident population. The second is the set of Contextual Databases (CDB) that provide information on macrolevel factors influencing demographic trends. By pursuing a multidisciplinary and comparative approach, GGP reveals much more about demographic behaviours and offers explanations and solutions with respect to current demographic changes and their consequences. Fourteen UNECE countries and two countries outside the UNECE region are currently implementing GGP (UNECE, 2008).

GGP Belgium is part of the international programme launched by the UNECE Population Activities Unit. The implementation is financially supported by Belgian Science Policy within the AGORA-programme, Statistics Belgium (ADSEI/DGSIE), the Studiedienst van de Vlaamse Regering (SVR) and the Institut Wallon de l'Évaluation, de la Prospective et de la Statistique (IWEPS). The scientific team supporting GGP Belgium consists of researchers from the following research centres: Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB), Universiteit Antwerpen (UA), Universiteit Gent (UGent), Université Catholique de Louvain (UCL), Studiedienst van de Vlaamse Regering (SVR), Institut Wallon de l'Évaluation, de la Prospective et de la Statistique (IWEPS) and the Association pour le Développement de la Recherche Appliquée en Sciences Sociales (ADRASS).

United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, Population Activity Unit:
<http://live.unece.org/pau/ggp/welcome.html>

Generations & Gender Programme:
<http://www.ggp-i.org>

2 Introduction

This paper focuses on the special codes declared during the GGP survey. The special codes included as answers to some of the questions are “Does not know” (“DNK”), “Refusal” and “Not applicable” (“NA”). These codes in fact correspond with missing and therefore unusable data. How frequently do these codes occur in GGP? To what extent has the applied “recovery” procedure of the special codes yielded good results? How the special codes are distributed across the interviews? These are the main issues that will be addressed in this paper, after briefly describing the various special codes as well as the so-called “recovery” procedure.

3 Special codes in GGP

3.1 The three special codes

Depending on the question, three special codes were proposed in the lists of response items:

- “Does not know” (DNK): by answering this, the interviewee states that he does not know the answer to the asked question. In the GGP database, this kind of answer is encoded by a number ending in 7, varying in length according to other answer categories in the question: « 7 » ; « 97 » ; « 997 » ; etc.
- “Refusal” (no abbreviated in this paper): by answering this, the interviewee states that he refuses to answer the question even if he knows the answer. This kind of answer is encoded by a number ending in 8: « 8 » ; « 98 » ; « 998 » ; etc.
- “Not applicable” (NA): by answering this, the interviewee states that, given his situation, he finds that the question is not relevant for him. This kind of answer is encoded by a number ending in 9: « 9 » ; « 99 » ; « 999 » ; etc.

The answers “DNK” and “Refusal” were available for the large majority of the questions. The exceptions were questions for which the answers were required to conduct the interview correctly (i. e; follow a correct routing). Question 1.13 for example, on the gender of the interviewee, should be answered compulsory. Without a correct answer on this question, some parts of the questionnaire could not be adapted to the interviewee’s situation, such as in module 5 (Fertility). Another example: question 1.33 refers to the interviewee’s current situation with regard to his activity. Not answering this question would imply that module 8 (Interviewee’s Activity and Income) could not be adapted to his activity status. We did not draw up the complete list of questions for which DNK and Refusal were not available. However, these questions are rather rare in the GGP survey.

Code “NA” is less frequently available as a possible answer. In fact, it is only proposed when the interviewee can, depending on his personal situation, decide that the question is not relevant for him (without the software having detected it, in which case the question would not have been asked). For example question 2.3.e that asks about assisting children in doing their homework. If there is no child in the household of an age at which the child has homework to be done, the interviewee could choose the “NA” answer option. Another example of this situation is question 2.40, about the age at which a child has stopped living

with the interviewee. The option “NA” could be selected by the interviewee if the child never lived with the interviewee.

3.2 The “recovery” questions

The special codes correspond with missing and therefore unusable data. Consequently, during the development of the questionnaire, the decision was taken to implement a strategy to reduce their occurrence. This strategy refers to questions on the dating of events and to amount of money:

- when a question on the date of an event was answered with DNK or Refusal, in the next question the age at the moment of the event was asked. The purpose is to replace certain missings on the year by a usable answer in terms of age. For example, in case of DNK or Refusal, question 1.22 (on the date at which the interviewee moved to Belgium) was followed by question 1.23 (on the age at which the interviewee moved to Belgium);
- in certain circumstances (usually questions on income), if the question referred to an amount of money and in case of Refusal or of DNK, the following question asked to provide an estimated amount. For example, question 8.96 asks the exact amount of the interviewee’s monthly income and question 8.97 asks an estimate of the income (249 € or less; 250 to 499 €; 500 to 999 €; etc.).

In the following, the question on the exact date or amount will be called “initial question”. The question on the age or estimated amount will be called “subsidiary question”.

It should be noted that the terms “variable” and “question” are used as synonyms in the rest of this text, although a variable is in fact the answer to a question. For example, if a question is about the year of an event, the corresponding variable will be the answer to this question. The adjectives “initial” and “subsidiary” are therefore applicable to both the “variable” and the “question”.

4 The frequency of the special codes in GGP: an overall approach

In this part, the frequency of the special codes will be discussed comprehensively, i.e. for all questions and interviews together. Afterwards, this aspect will be addressed by category of questions (part C) and then by interview (part D). To conduct these analyses, three counts of special codes have been carried out:

- the first count covers all variables of all interviews;
- the second count excludes all subsidiary variables, which in a sense overlap with the initial variable as they refer to the same subject but express the data in another way;
- the third count replaces the initial variables by a combination of these initial variables and the subsidiary variables. The purpose of this combination is to replace, wherever possible, a special code of an initial variable by a usable value from a subsidiary variable. With this third count, it is possible to estimate the additional usable data obtained through the subsidiary questions.

Table 1 shows the results of these three counts. In this table, “Active questions” refer to questions that have actually been asked. The questionnaire is adapted to the situation of each interviewee by means of a filter system based on what is already known about the interviewee when the question is asked.

Table 1: The three counts of the special codes

	1st count (all questions of all interviews)		2nd count (excluding all subsidiary questions)		3rd count (combination of initial and subsidiary questions)	
	Absolute number	%	Absolute number	%	Absolute number	%
Active questions	2,977,908	100.00%	2,898,434	100.00%	2,898,434	100.00%
DNK	37,754	1.27%	35,077	1.21%	27,164	0.94%
Refusal	9,454	0.32%	8,273	0.29%	7,535	0.26%
NA	50,188	1.69%	50,188	1.73%	50,188	1.73%
DNK, Refusal and NA	97,396	3.27%	93,538	3.23%	84,887	2.93%

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

According to the first count, a total of 2,977,908 questions have been asked to 7,163 individuals interviewed for the GGP survey, which equals an average of 415.7 questions per interview. This first count provides a first important observation: in contrast to the fear that the GGP survey would include too many sensitive questions (questions on the income, financial transfers as well as some “intimate” behaviour) resulting in high numbers of missing values, the number of “Refusals” is small, more specifically 0.32 %, or slightly more than one question on average per interview.

Table 2 is based on table 1 and allows a comparison between the first and second counts on the one hand, and the second and third counts on the other hand. For example “2nd count – 3rd count” indicates the difference between the number of special codes registered during the 2nd and the 3rd counts. More specifically, in the DNK row, 7,913 = 35,077 – 27,164: there are in the 3rd count 7,913 instances of usable data more than in the 2nd count. The percentage of this decrease in the number of DNK compared to the 2nd count amounts to 22.56 % (7,913/35,077). It should be noted that in this second table and the following ones, the NA row has been deleted given the stable number of individuals associated with this code.

Table 2: Comparisons between the three counts of the special codes

	1st count – 2nd count		2nd count – 3rd count	
	Absolute number	%	Absolute number	%
Active questions	79,474	2.67%	-	-
DNK	2,677	7.09%	7,913	22.56%
Refusal	1,181	12.49%	738	8.92%
DNK and Refusal	3,858	3.96%	8,651	9.25%

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

It should be reminded that the 1st count includes both initial and subsidiary questions, which are all about the same topic. The subsidiary questions were thus withdrawn in the 2nd count. The number of questions declines from 2,977,908 to 2,898,434 **between the 1st and the 2nd count**. This is a decrease by 79,747 questions or 2.67 % of the initial volume (table 2). Therefore, the average number of questions asked per interview falls from 415.7 to 404.6, indicating that, on average, 11 subsidiary questions have been asked per interview. The percentages of DNK and Refusals decrease very slightly with the withdrawal of the subsidiary questions and go down from 1.27 to 1.21 % and 0.32 to 0.29 % for respectively DNK and Refusals (table 1). Conversely, the percentage of NA increases from 1.69 to 1.73 % (table 1). This disparity in trends can be easily explained:

- the NA code did not result in an increase of subsidiary question and was not an option in those subsidiary questions. Therefore, between the 1st and the 2nd counts, the denominator of the percentage has decreased as a result of the decline in the number of questions asked while the numerator did not change since all NA have been kept;
- the percentages of DNK and Refusals decreased between counts 1 and 2. The number of questions has indeed decreased by 2.67 % but the number of DNK and Refusals has decreased more remarkably, by respectively 7.09 % and 12.49 % (table 2).

The comparison between the 2nd and the 3rd count allows quantifying the efficiency of the use of the subsidiary questions in removing the unusable data from the initial variables. Indeed, the difference between these two counts gives an accurate picture of the data that have become usable thanks to the subsidiary questions. It is therefore useful to thoroughly analyse the differences between the 2nd and 3rd count (section C).

Between the 2nd and 3rd count, the percentages of DNK and Refusals compared to the number of questions asked have decreased from 1.21 % to 0.94 % for the DNK and from 0.29 % to 0.26 % for the Refusals (table 1). Thanks to the combination of the initial and subsidiary questions, 7,913 DNK and 738 Refusals have become usable values. As, at the same time, the number of questions asked did not change, the percentages of DNK and Refusals are obviously decreasing (table 1).

Still, between the 2nd and the 3rd count, subsidiary questions allowed reducing the absolute number of DNK and Refusals by respectively nearly 23 and 9% (table 2). More detailed data on this subject are needed to fine-tune the analysis of the efficiency of the subsidiary questions. This is what we are going to do in the following section.

5 Focus on the reduction of special codes thanks to the recovery questions

Table 3 allows a more accurate analysis of the procedure aimed at reducing the frequency of special codes through subsidiary questions. Here are a few indications to read this table 3:

- Table 3 includes 4 sub-tables :
 - a. “Total”: counts of all variables ;
 - b. “Combined monetary data”: counts of only the monetary variables which have given rise to a subsidiary question and therefore to a combination of initial and subsidiary values;
 - c. “Combined dates”: idem but for date variables ;
 - d. “Other not combined”: counts of all variables which have not given rise to a subsidiary question;
- columns (1) and (2): numbers of active questions, DNK and Refusal (partly included in table 1);
- column (3): difference in number of special codes between 2nd and 3rd count;
- columns (4), (5) and (6): these columns show what happened to the special codes after combination of the initial and subsidiary variables. For example, for the variables included in table 3b, the 4,499 DNK identified in the 2nd count are broken down as follows in the 3rd count:
 - a. 1,436 DNK confirmed between the two counts (column 4);
 - b. 72 Refusals (column 5) ;
 - c. 2,991 usable values (“UV” in column 6):
 - d. Finally: $4,499 = 1,436 + 72 + 2,991$;
 - e. the number of DNK in the 3rd count amounts to 1,501 (column 2), simply because 65 Refusals became DNK after combination (column 4, row of the Refusals): $1,501 = 1,436 + 65$;
- column (7): the proportion of special codes of the 2nd count which became usable values after combination. Referring to the example of the DNK row of table 3.b: 66.48 % of the initial DNK became usable data after combination, or $2,991/4,499$.

Table 3: Reduction of the special codes, 2nd and 3rd counts.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	2 nd count	3 rd count	(1)-(2)	DNK	Refusal	→ UV	(6) in % of (1)
a. Total							
Active questions	2,898,434	2,898,434	0	-	-	-	
DNK	35,077	27,164	7,913	-	103	7,898	22.52%
Refusal	8,273	7,535	738	88	-	753	9.10%
b. Combined monetary data							
Active questions	19,787	19,787	0	-	-	-	-
DNK	4,499	1,501	2,998	1,436	72	2,991	66.48%
Refusal	1,596	956	640	65	884	647	40.54%
c. Combined dates							
Active questions	137,948	137,948	0	-	-	-	-
DNK	6,161	1,246	4,915	1,223	31	4,907	79.65%
Refusal	337	239	98	23	208	106	31.45%
d. Other not combined							
Active questions	2,740,699	2,740,699	0	-	-	-	-
DNK	24,417	24,417	0	-	0	0	0.00%
Refusal	6,340	6,340	0	0	-	0	0.00%

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

In table 3, variables subject to a possible combination were isolated from others and a distinction was made according to whether they were a date or a monetary amount. Indeed:

- these variables are the only variables involved in the combination procedure, the effectiveness of which we want to assess. It is therefore necessary to isolate them in order to see the impact of the recovery procedure only when it was potentially active;
- depending on the nature of the variable, the procedure is likely to reveal a different efficiency: date and financial amount variables can generate very different reactions during the interview like, for example, a greater or deeper reluctance to reveal the amount of the income than the date of any event.

In table 3, the recovery procedure of usable data by means of a subsidiary question was proven to be efficient: 66.48 and 79.65 % of the initial 'DNK' answers to the questions on respectively monetary amounts and dates became usable data. Although the proportions are lower for the Refusals, they are far from negligible with respectively 40.54 % and 31.45 % for the questions on monetary amounts and dates. The combination was therefore more efficient in reducing the 'DNK' answers for the questions on dates than for questions on monetary amounts: 79.65% of usable new values for dates compared to only 66.48% for monetary amounts. The opposite situation prevails for Refusals, with 31.45 % compared to 40.54 %.

Table 4: What happened at the third count with the DNK and Refusals of the second count?

	2 nd count	3 rd count absolute numbers			3 rd count relative value			
		→ DNK	Refusal	→ UV	→ DNK	Refusal	→ UV	Total
b. Combined monetary data								
DNK	4,499	1,436	72	2,991	31.92%	1.60%	66.48%	100.00%
Refusal	1,596	65	884	647	4.07%	55.39%	40.54%	100.00%
c. Combined dates								
DNK	6,161	1,223	31	4,907	19.85%	0.50%	79.65%	100.00%
Refusal	337	23	208	106	6.82%	61.72%	31.45%	100.00%

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

This contrast probably reflects an influence of the question type. A Refusal would be more easily confirmed for dates, as it indicates a relatively firm intention not to address this issue. Conversely, in case of monetary amounts, the vagueness introduced by the subsidiary question asking a range of amount would reduce the intrusive character perceived by respondents who would therefore be more willing to convert their initial Refusal. Table 4 confirms this hypothesis: it shows that, for dates, 62 % of the Refusals in the second count are confirmed in the 3rd count compared to only 55 % for amounts¹.

For the DNK, it is possible that this initially proposed answer really corresponds to a greater ignorance of the amounts than of the dates. On the contrary, for dates, the answer converted into age would become more accessible than for the amounts. Table 4 confirms this hypothesis: for the amounts, 32% DNK are confirmed between the 2nd and the 3rd count compared to only 20% for the dates.

These considerations could usefully try to incorporate a possible strategy of the interviewees: instead of refusing to answer the initial question, some people may have opted for "DNK" assuming that a Refusal is a harder and more aggressive attitude towards the interviewer than admitting that they do not know. These 'false' DNK (disguised Refusals so to speak) would be confirmed in the subsidiary question given that the Refusals are more often confirmed than the DNK. These considerations have not been further investigated in this paper.

After this analysis of the gains in usable data, we are going to investigate whether the procedure introducing subsidiary questions is interesting for the survey. These questions make the questionnaire heavier. Did this effort pay off? As already mentioned, the benefit is very clear for the DNK: two thirds of the initial DNK for amounts and 80% of the initial DNK for dates become usable data (table 4). For the Refusals, the result remains positive, although less impressive: 41% gain for the amounts and 31% for the dates. The benefits of the procedure are therefore undeniable: when this procedure was active, the proportion of initially unusable data could be significantly reduced.

¹ The table 4 could seem to be in contradiction with previous tables. See appendix 2.

6 The frequency of the special codes by interview

6.1 Introduction

This section focuses on the analysis of the DNK, Refusals and NA by interview. We analyse the percentages of these response categories by interview (and no longer by variable or variable category). Analyses have been conducted by module and in total. Moreover, in order to assess the influence of the presence of one or more third person(s) on the percentages of DNK, Refusals and NA, the results were broken down according to whether the interviewee was alone or not when the questions of this module were asked and according to the characteristics of this or these possible third person(s).

The analyzed data are based on the third count, at which the data of the subsidiary questions allowed to reduce the number of unusable data (section A.2). After counting of the special codes, these initial results are expressed as percentages of the number of active questions during the interviews. Full (about the 3 special codes) and detailed (breakdown into 9 percentage classes) results of this procedure are available in appendix, as well as by module and in total.

In this very wide set of results, we decided to focus on the analysis of the Refusals. Indeed, the DNK and NA (provided that are not too often actual Refusals) reveal situations that are in fact very different from a Refusal: a Refusal expresses the deliberate intention not to provide the information (even if it is known) while a DNK is the result of a natural process of ignorance and a NA corresponds to the fact that the individual logically believes that the question is not applicable to him because of his specific situation.

Before analysing and discussing the results, we also draw the attention to the fact that a Refusal can neutralize a series of questions which may have an important influence on the counts. So, if the answer to question 8.3 (about the status) in the module 8 is a Refusal, questions 8.4 to 8.52 are automatically not asked. Similarly, if question 8.53 (activity during the week before the interview) results in a Refusal, questions 8.54 to 8.93 are not asked. So, after two questions resulting in a Refusal, the interview already comes to an end for this module 8!

In the analyses that we have made here, no hierarchy was created between Refusals: a Refusal to a question that does not affect the rest of the interview has the same weight as a question opening a sequence of questions. However, the latter situation could be regarded as a number of Refusals equivalent to the number of passed over questions. Therefore, the absolute number of Refusals to be recorded would increase, but not the number of interviews without Refusal. A similar situation is found for the DNK, in certain circumstances, a DNK neutralized one, some or many following question(s).

6.2 Percentage of interviews without Refusal by module

To analyze this aspect, it was decided to take the percentage of interviews without any Refusal as an indicator of the frequency of Refusals. Table 5 shows the percentages of interviews without Refusal first by module and then for all modules. A distinction was made between interviews that were conducted in the presence of one or several third person(s) (and whether this person was the wife/husband/partner) and those where no one else was present. Figure 1 was generated on the basis of these data. The absolute numbers of persons involved in each module were not added in table 5, for the simple reason that it varies from one module to another (these numbers are available in appendix 1).

Table 5: Percentages of interview without Refusal by module (3rd count)

	No 3 rd per.	3 rd pers. without partner	3 rd pers. including partner	Total
Module 1	99.35%	99.57%	99.70%	99.41%
Module 2	99.32%	98.63%	99.29%	99.27%
Module 3	95.02%	90.44%	97.63%	95.14%
Module 4	98.62%	96.70%	96.82%	98.23%
Module 5	88.68%	86.18%	93.00%	89.19%
Module 6	98.92%	96.98%	99.55%	98.91%
Module 7	99.03%	97.82%	99.01%	98.95%
Module 8	94.52%	96.59%	94.07%	94.57%
Module 9	95.64%	94.94%	94.83%	95.49%
Module 10	92.53%	92.52%	90.26%	92.17%
Module 11	94.21%	93.52%	93.56%	94.07%
Modules 1 to 11	72.31%	66.83%	75.09%	72.46%

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

Generally, the percentages of interviews without Refusal are high to very high. However the situation is somewhat less favourable for three modules with percentages much lower than 95 % as can be seen in table 5 and figure 1. In module 5 (Fertility), in addition to encoding problems for some questions, Refusals concern questions on medical matters (infertility, problems during pregnancy, use of contraception...) and the fertility intentions. Beyond the absolute number of Refusals, the proportion of Refusals for some questions is particularly striking. For example, in question 5.34 (date at which the interviewee has learned that he/she could (probably) not have any children), there are 29 Refusals, which seems to be low, but on a total of 200 cases, this is almost 15%.

Figure 1: Percentages of interviews without Refusal by module

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

In module 10 (Total Household Income), the questions on income generate the highest number of Refusals, especially when the amounts are asked. So, for question 11.10 (total household income), there are 392 Refusals in 7,163 interviews and for question 11.16 (amount of money received from a person, limited to the first donation (question 11.16_1)), 99 Refusals in 525 answers, or nearly 19%. It should be noted that, in modules 8 and 9 (Interviewee's and Partner's Activity and Income), in which questions deal with income, there are also a lot of interviews without Refusal. This trend is less pronounced in module 10.

In module 11 (Values and Attitudes), the number of Refusals ranges from 5 to 20 for almost every question. Some questions are characterised by a higher number of Refusals (30 to over 50) without any possibility to identify real trends on the more sensitive topics as they cover a wide range of themes. Moreover, it is interesting to note that there were very few Refusals for question 11.3 (belonging to a religion or not) although this question might have seem particularly intrusive.

Finally, in module 3 (Children), the proportion of interviews without Refusal is very close to 95%. Some sub-questions of question 3.87 (advantages and disadvantages of starting living together with the current non-cohabiting partner in the next three years) are characterized by 40 to 75 Refusals. The same situation is found for question 3.88 (factors involved in the decision to start living together with the current non-cohabiting partner in the next three years) but at a lower level (between 12 and 20 Refusals). In module 3, question 3.92 received 35 Refusals, which means that the interviewee refuses to talk about past episodes in his life as a couple. Therefore, questions 3.93 to 3.126, which were to be asked for each reported episode, were automatically bypassed.

Figure 1 also gives more insight into the effect of the presence of a third person at the beginning of the interview (modules 2 to 7) if one or several third person(s) are present but not the partner. Conversely, at the end of the interview (modules 8, 9 and 10), the lowest percentages are recorded when the partner is present. Despite these findings, the graph is characterised by a tangled web of curves: the presence or absence of third person(s) and the type of third person(s) has no marked and/or systematic influence on the percentage of interviews without Refusal.

6.3 Percentage of interviews without Refusal all modules

Table 6 shows the breakdown of the interviews (module 1 to 11) according to the percentage of Refusals and not only the percentage of interviews without Refusal). 72% of the interviews were conducted without any Refusal. Moreover, there were Refusals in 22% of the interviews but in less than 1% of the active questions. Above 1% of active questions, percentages decrease rapidly and become negligible: 0.38 % for 5-<10 %! In short, Refusals are rare in the GGP survey.

Table 6: Breakdown of the interviews by percentage of Refusals (modules 1 to 11)

	No third person	Third person, without partner	Third person, including partner	Total
0 %	72.31%	66.83%	75.09%	72.46%
0% > < 1%	21.78%	22.19%	21.22%	21.71%
1% < 2%	3.27%	4.74%	2.32%	3.20%
2% < 5%	2.05%	5.24%	0.60%	2.00%
5% < 10%	0.32%	0.75%	0.52%	0.38%
10% < 20%	0.23%	0.25%	0.09%	0.21%
20% < 30%	0.02%	0.00%	0.09%	0.03%
30% < 40%	0.02%	0.00%	0.00%	0.01%
40% < 100%	0.00%	0.00%	0.09%	0.01%
100%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Total number	5 598	401	1 164	7 163

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

There are relatively more Refusals when third persons apart from the partner are present: the percentage of interviews without Refusal falls from 72 % to 67% but is compensated by higher proportions of interviews with 1 to 20% Refusals. If the partner is one of the third persons the situation is actually better: more than three quarters of the interviews are without Refusal.

Does the gender of the interviewee have an influence on the percentage of interviews without Refusal? As shown in table 7, the total percentages of interviews without any Refusal are quite similar for both genders: 71.70 % for men compared to 73.15 % for women, or a difference « women minus men » of 1.45 %. If the interview was conducted without a third person, women (73.78 %) still have higher percentages than men (70.62 %), or a difference of 3.17 %. If one or several third person(s) was/were present but not the partner, the gap

increases to 5.63 % compared to men. On the other hand, the presence of the spouse has the opposite effect: women have then the lowest percentage, with a difference of -6.19 %.

Table 7: Percentage of interviews without Refusals (modules 1 to 11) – by gender

	No third person	Third person, without partner	Third person, including partner	Total
Men	70.62%	63.27%	77.62%	71.70%
Women	73.78%	68.90%	71.43%	73.15%
Total	72.31%	66.83%	75.09%	72.46%
Difference (W-M)	3.17%	5.63%	-6.19%	1.45%

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

Overall, as long as the partner is not present during the interview, women have higher percentages of interviews without Refusal than men. But the presence of the partner results in a lower percentage of interviews without Refusal among women than among men. Quite surprisingly at first sight, at least in our opinion, the lowest percentage of interviews without Refusal is recorded when third persons are present but not the partner; it is as if the presence of the partner is less likely to inhibit the interviewee than the presence of other individuals.

6.4 The concentration of Refusals

How are the Refusals distributed among the interviews? Are there « specialists » in Refusal?

To answer these questions, table 8 shows the distribution of interviews by number of Refusals and the distribution of the number of actual Refusals by the number of Refusals per interview. Table 8 has been drawn up on the basis of the third count. Of course, 72.5 % of interviews are without any Refusal (tables 5 and 8). Nearly 90% of the interviews were conducted with less than 3 Refusals, 95% with less than 5 Refusals and 99.5% with 21 Refusals or less.

Cases with 25 Refusals and more might be considered as exceptional. Indeed, table 8 shows that:

- distribution is no longer continuous, as after 25 Refusals the following case has 28 Refusals (column 2 of table 8);
- among interviews with more than 25 Refusals, there are two cases with 29, 30, 32 and 45 Refusals; all other results were observed only once (column 2 of table 8), which emphasizes that these cases are exceptional;
- in terms of number of interviews, these cases with more than 25 Refusals represent only 0.40 % of the interviews (column 4 of table 8), or 29 interviews in 7,163, but almost 22% of the actual Refusals (column 7 of table 6)!

The distribution, which is far from equal, reveals that some interviews are "specialized" in Refusals. Due to the unavailability of certain data (especially the identification number of the interviewer), it was however impossible to determine whether this situation is caused by the interviewees or the interviewers.

Table 8: The specialists in Refusal: Refusal by interview (modules 1 to 11)

(1)	Number of interviews			Number of Refusals		
	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
Number of Refusals	Number of cases	(2)/sum(2)	Cumulative % of (3)	(1)*(2)	(5)/sum(5)	Cumulative % of (6)
0	5,190	72.5%	72.5%	0	0.0%	0.0%
1	846	11.8%	84.3%	846	11.2%	11.2%
2	419	5.8%	90.1%	838	11.1%	22.3%
3	246	3.4%	93.6%	738	9.8%	32.1%
4	114	1.6%	95.1%	456	6.1%	38.2%
5	77	1.1%	96.2%	385	5.1%	43.3%
6	48	0.7%	96.9%	288	3.8%	47.1%
7	30	0.4%	97.3%	210	2.8%	49.9%
8	19	0.3%	97.6%	152	2.0%	51.9%
9	13	0.2%	97.8%	117	1.6%	53.5%
10	13	0.2%	97.9%	130	1.7%	55.2%
11	12	0.2%	98.1%	132	1.8%	57.0%
12	12	0.2%	98.3%	144	1.9%	58.9%
13	43	0.6%	98.9%	559	7.4%	66.3%
14	9	0.1%	99.0%	126	1.7%	68.0%
15	6	0.1%	99.1%	90	1.2%	69.2%
16	13	0.2%	99.3%	208	2.8%	71.9%
17	5	0.1%	99.3%	85	1.1%	73.0%
18	2	0.0%	99.4%	36	0.5%	73.5%
19	4	0.1%	99.4%	76	1.0%	74.5%
20	1	0.0%	99.4%	20	0.3%	74.8%
21	3	0.0%	99.5%	63	0.8%	75.6%
22	4	0.1%	99.5%	88	1.2%	76.8%
23	1	0.0%	99.5%	23	0.3%	77.1%
24	3	0.0%	99.6%	72	1.0%	78.1%
25	1	0.0%	99.6%	25	0.3%	78.4%
28	1	0.0%	99.6%	28	0.4%	78.8%
29	2	0.0%	99.6%	58	0.8%	79.5%
30	2	0.0%	99.7%	60	0.8%	80.3%
32	2	0.0%	99.7%	64	0.8%	81.2%
33	1	0.0%	99.7%	33	0.4%	81.6%
36	1	0.0%	99.7%	36	0.5%	82.1%
38	1	0.0%	99.7%	38	0.5%	82.6%
39	1	0.0%	99.7%	39	0.5%	83.1%
41	1	0.0%	99.8%	41	0.5%	83.7%
44	1	0.0%	99.8%	44	0.6%	84.2%
45	2	0.0%	99.8%	90	1.2%	85.4%
46	1	0.0%	99.8%	46	0.6%	86.1%
47	1	0.0%	99.8%	47	0.6%	86.7%
48	1	0.0%	99.8%	48	0.6%	87.3%
51	1	0.0%	99.9%	51	0.7%	88.0%
55	1	0.0%	99.9%	55	0.7%	88.7%
56	1	0.0%	99.9%	56	0.7%	89.5%
58	1	0.0%	99.9%	58	0.8%	90.2%
60	1	0.0%	99.9%	60	0.8%	91.0%
72	1	0.0%	99.9%	72	1.0%	92.0%
73	1	0.0%	99.9%	73	1.0%	93.0%
90	1	0.0%	100.0%	90	1.2%	94.1%
93	1	0.0%	100.0%	93	1.2%	95.4%
116	1	0.0%	100.0%	116	1.5%	96.9%
232	1	0.0%	100.0%	232	3.1%	100.0%
Total	7,163	100.0%	-	7,535	100.0%	-

Source: GGS Belgium, Wave 1 - Calculations by authors

7 Conclusions

The presence of special codes for Refusals, DNK or NA may cause difficulties when analysing the results. Their presence in the data must be reduced wherever possible even if they may sometimes also be of interest for analysis, revealing some aspects of the behaviour of individuals about the issue.

Despite fears rising during the preparation of the questionnaire that some questions would be particularly "intrusive" in some aspects of life, Refusals and DNK are few in the GGP survey. In our opinion, their presence does not affect the validity of the analyses based on the survey data. To refine these comments, it should be checked whether:

- some characteristics of the respondents, such as education or income level, influence the frequency of special codes;
- some interviewers are « specialized » in this kind of answers.

Moreover, the recovery questions allowed drastically reducing the number of Refusals and DNK. So, for the monetary variables for which the recovery procedure was applicable the number of DNK has been reduced by 66% and the number of Refusals by 41 %; for the date variables, the same numbers have been reduced by respectively 80 and 31%.

The analysis of the special codes showed that some modules were more affected than others, depending among others on the presence of some kinds of questions. In module 3 (Children), the presence of questions on the advantages and disadvantages, as well as the factors that influence the start of a shared life with the non-cohabiting partner, explains the relatively low percentage of interviews without Refusal. In module 5 (Fertility), besides encoding problems, the Refusals were recorded in questions on medical issues and intentions regarding fertility. In module 10 (Total Household Income), the questions on income reduce the proportion of interviews without Refusal. The same phenomenon occurs in modules 8 and 9 for the same reasons but to a smaller extent. Finally, in module 11 (Values and Attitudes), all question have a slightly higher proportion of Refusals, but to varying degrees.

Depending on the gender, the frequency of Refusals varies especially according to the circumstances of the interview and more particularly the kind of third person who also attended the interview.

These findings do not undermine the main conclusion of this analysis, in the GGP survey, special codes, and especially Refusals and DNK, are rather rare.

8 Appendices

8.1 Counts and miscounts of the subsidiary questions

Table 4 shows that 12,593 subsidiary questions were actually asked: 4,449 DNK and 1,596 Refusals for monetary variables, and 6,161 DNK and 337 Refusals for date variables. According to the explanations given to the recovery questions (see A.2), these DNK and Refusals should have been followed by a subsidiary question on age or on a range of monetary amounts. In table 2 however, the difference between counts 1 and 2 is 79,474. This number seems to suggest that 79,474 subsidiary questions were asked and that these questions were removed between counts 1 and 2. There is thus a difference of 66,881 (79,474-12,593). How explain this difference?

For some pairs of variables concerned by the recovery procedure, the mechanism has worked exactly as described. For example, 104 DNK and 10 Refusals were recorded for questions PA3YY and PA4 (respectively on date and age at the beginning of the relationship with the cohabiting spouse or partner). Subsidiary question PA4 was therefore asked 114 times

The situation is different for other pairs of variables such as questions HH14YY_2 and HH15_2 (respectively on date of birth and age of the second household member). There were 100 DNK and 7 Refusals for question HH14YY_2. Question HH15_2 should have been asked 107 times. However, variable HH15_2 has 6,182 values. This is the number of times that question HH15YY_2 has been asked. This is simply due to the fact that, during the interview, age was calculated automatically whenever possible (or whenever the year of birth was known). Age was namely necessary to adapt certain parts of the questionnaire to the situation of the dependent person. So, in 6,075 cases, variable HH15_2 includes an age calculated from a date (HH14YY_2) while subsidiary question HH15_2 was actually not asked.

We did not systematically count all pairs of questions for which the number of values exceeded the number of times the subsidiary question was actually asked. This mechanism explains the above-mentioned difference of 66,881.

8.2 'Does not know', 'Refusal' and 'Not applicable' by module

The percentages obtained by the procedure described in section 6.1 have been grouped into the following classes:

0 = '0 %'	5 = 'From 10% to less than 20%'
1 = 'From 0% to less than 1%'	6 = 'From 20% to less than 30%'
2 = 'From 1% to less than 2%'	7 = 'From 30% to less than 40%'
3 = 'From 2% to less than 5%'	8 = 'From 40% to less than 100%'
4 = 'From 5% to less than 10%'	9 = '100%'

A careful reading of the results may suggest some remarkable situations. For example, in the sub-table of the Refusals of module 5, the rows « 0% > < 1% » and « 1% – < 2% » report 0 percentages contrary to the preceding and following rows. The number of active variables in this module varies from 25 to 61 according to the interviews. Moreover, interviews with only one Refusal only occur among interviews with fewer than 41 active questions. Therefore, the minimum percentage of Refusals beyond 0 is 2.50%. This explains the 0% of the rows « 0% > < 1% » and « 1% – < 2% ».

Another possibly surprising situation was found: in module 8, an interview has 100% Refusals. It is actually an interview with very few active variables for which the answer was systematically a Refusal, which makes that many other questions of the module were bypassed. This highlights an important point: a Refusal to some questions neutralizes many other questions. So, in the interview with 100% Refusals in module 8, the answer to question 8.3 (confirmation of previous answer to a question about the activity status) was a Refusal; therefore, questions 8.4 to 8.52 were not asked. The answer to 8.53 (activity during the week before the interview) was also a Refusal; questions 8.54 to 8.93 were therefore not asked. This situation with 100% Refusals and relatively few active variables is found in other modules but for small numbers of interviews.

No hierarchy of the Refusals has been established in the analyses that have been made: a Refusal to a question which does not affect the rest of the interview has the same weight as a question opening a range of questions, while the latter could be seen as equivalent to the number of bypassed questions, which would increase the number of counted Refusals. The same situation occurs with the DNK: under certain circumstances, a DNK can neutralize one or several questions.

In some modules, such as the first, all interviews were conducted without any NA. This is not always the case. NA answers occur in module 2 for example.

The last 4 tables of the annex show the results of the 11 modules together. For those four tables, the presence or absence of a third person has been determined from the situation in module 11. This is the module where the presence of a third person was the most frequent (excepted module 3).

Title of the columns:

- « Pas de tierce p. » = « No third person »
- « Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt » = « Third person(s) present but not the partner »
- « Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt » = « Third person(s) present including at least the partner »

Ne sait pas (%)					Ne sait pas (%)				
Module 1	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 2	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	84,68%	82,72%	85,96%	84,73%	0 %	87,27%	90,89%	86,13%	87,34%
0% > < 1%	0,02%	0,00%	0,10%	0,03%	0% > < 1%	0,05%	0,00%	0,10%	0,06%
1% < 2%	4,48%	6,26%	4,14%	4,55%	1% < 2%	0,85%	0,68%	1,11%	0,88%
2% < 5%	7,76%	8,42%	7,88%	7,82%	2% < 5%	5,65%	3,64%	6,48%	5,64%
5% < 10%	2,78%	2,59%	1,82%	2,64%	5% < 10%	4,31%	3,42%	4,66%	4,30%
10% < 20%	0,28%	0,00%	0,10%	0,24%	10% < 20%	1,52%	1,14%	1,32%	1,47%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20% < 30%	0,26%	0,23%	0,10%	0,24%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,07%	0,00%	0,10%	0,07%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.710	463	990	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.736	439	988	7.163

Refus (%)					Refus (%)				
Module 1	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 2	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	99,35%	99,57%	99,70%	99,41%	0 %	99,32%	98,63%	99,29%	99,27%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
1% < 2%	0,19%	0,43%	0,00%	0,18%	1% < 2%	0,07%	0,00%	0,00%	0,06%
2% < 5%	0,35%	0,00%	0,20%	0,31%	2% < 5%	0,19%	0,68%	0,30%	0,24%
5% < 10%	0,07%	0,00%	0,10%	0,07%	5% < 10%	0,24%	0,23%	0,30%	0,25%
10% < 20%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	10% < 20%	0,10%	0,23%	0,10%	0,11%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,02%	0,23%	0,00%	0,03%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.710	463	990	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.736	439	988	7.163

Pas d'application (%)					Pas d'application (%)				
Module 1	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 2	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	0 %	88,13%	81,09%	83,70%	87,07%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,23%	0,10%	0,03%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1% < 2%	0,38%	0,23%	0,40%	0,38%
2% < 5%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	2% < 5%	4,50%	7,97%	7,19%	5,08%
5% < 10%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	5% < 10%	4,45%	7,52%	5,47%	4,77%
10% < 20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	10% < 20%	2,37%	2,73%	3,14%	2,50%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20% < 30%	0,17%	0,00%	0,00%	0,14%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,23%	0,00%	0,01%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	99,98%	100,00%	100,00%	99,99%
Eff. Tot.	5.710	463	990	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.735	439	988	7.162

Ne sait pas (%)					Ne sait pas (%)				
Module 3	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 4	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	52,76%	43,59%	67,85%	54,52%	0 %	96,91%	95,99%	96,18%	96,75%
0% > < 1%	0,27%	0,00%	0,00%	0,21%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	4,49%	5,13%	2,01%	4,15%	1% < 2%	0,04%	0,24%	0,00%	0,04%
2% < 5%	12,34%	13,75%	7,58%	11,70%	2% < 5%	2,29%	1,65%	3,28%	2,40%
5% < 10%	18,25%	23,54%	14,61%	18,01%	5% < 10%	0,48%	1,42%	0,45%	0,53%
10% < 20%	9,77%	10,02%	6,48%	9,28%	10% < 20%	0,16%	0,71%	0,09%	0,18%
20% < 30%	1,86%	3,73%	1,10%	1,86%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
30% < 40%	0,12%	0,23%	0,18%	0,14%	30% < 40%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%
40% < 100%	0,14%	0,00%	0,18%	0,14%	40% < 100%	0,07%	0,00%	0,00%	0,06%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.639	429	1.095	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.640	424	1.099	7.163

Refus (%)					Refus (%)				
Module 3	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 4	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	95,02%	90,44%	97,63%	95,14%	0 %	98,62%	96,70%	96,82%	98,23%
0% > < 1%	0,09%	0,23%	0,00%	0,08%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,99%	1,63%	0,37%	0,94%	1% < 2%	0,02%	0,24%	0,09%	0,04%
2% < 5%	1,61%	2,80%	0,82%	1,56%	2% < 5%	0,98%	1,89%	2,27%	1,23%
5% < 10%	1,33%	2,56%	0,91%	1,34%	5% < 10%	0,20%	1,18%	0,45%	0,29%
10% < 20%	0,53%	1,40%	0,09%	0,52%	10% < 20%	0,07%	0,00%	0,18%	0,08%
20% < 30%	0,11%	0,47%	0,09%	0,13%	20% < 30%	0,05%	0,00%	0,09%	0,06%
30% < 40%	0,09%	0,23%	0,00%	0,08%	30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
40% < 100%	0,21%	0,23%	0,09%	0,20%	40% < 100%	0,05%	0,00%	0,09%	0,06%
100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.639	429	1.095	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.640	424	1.099	7.163

Pas d'application (%)					Pas d'application (%)				
Module 3	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 4	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	58,22%	48,48%	82,47%	61,34%	0 %	51,88%	66,75%	22,75%	48,29%
0% > < 1%	0,34%	0,23%	0,09%	0,29%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	5,14%	6,76%	2,37%	4,82%	1% < 2%	0,09%	0,00%	0,18%	0,10%
2% < 5%	9,42%	13,29%	4,20%	8,85%	2% < 5%	19,93%	21,70%	23,11%	20,52%
5% < 10%	17,10%	16,08%	10,23%	15,98%	5% < 10%	17,94%	7,78%	28,30%	18,93%
10% < 20%	9,01%	13,52%	0,55%	7,99%	10% < 20%	9,93%	3,77%	24,75%	11,84%
20% < 30%	0,66%	1,63%	0,09%	0,63%	20% < 30%	0,16%	0,00%	0,82%	0,25%
30% < 40%	0,11%	0,00%	0,00%	0,08%	30% < 40%	0,07%	0,00%	0,09%	0,07%
40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.639	429	1.095	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.640	424	1.099	7.163

Title of the columns:

- « Pas de tierce p. » = « No third person »
- « Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt » = « Third person(s) present but not the partner »
- « Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt » = « Third person(s) present including at least the partner »

Ne sait pas (%)					Ne sait pas (%)				
Module 5	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 6	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	86,69%	83,42%	91,24%	87,20%	0 %	75,15%	70,35%	73,61%	74,65%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,09%	0,00%	0,00%	0,07%	1% < 2%	2,22%	3,02%	2,00%	2,23%
2% < 5%	9,82%	11,56%	6,91%	9,48%	2% < 5%	15,43%	19,60%	16,29%	15,79%
5% < 10%	2,29%	3,27%	1,29%	2,19%	5% < 10%	5,45%	6,03%	6,55%	5,65%
10% < 20%	0,55%	1,76%	0,28%	0,57%	10% < 20%	1,39%	0,50%	1,36%	1,34%
20% < 30%	0,16%	0,00%	0,09%	0,14%	20% < 30%	0,26%	0,50%	0,09%	0,25%
30% < 40%	0,05%	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%	30% < 40%	0,04%	0,00%	0,09%	0,04%
40% < 100%	0,32%	0,00%	0,00%	0,25%	40% < 100%	0,05%	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%
100%	0,04%	0,00%	0,18%	0,06%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.680	398	1.085	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.666	398	1.099	7.163

Refus (%)					Refus (%)				
Module 5	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 6	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	88,68%	86,18%	93,00%	89,19%	0 %	98,92%	96,98%	99,55%	98,91%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1% < 2%	0,09%	0,50%	0,00%	0,10%
2% < 5%	7,59%	8,29%	5,53%	7,32%	2% < 5%	0,76%	1,51%	0,27%	0,73%
5% < 10%	2,41%	2,51%	0,55%	2,14%	5% < 10%	0,14%	0,25%	0,00%	0,13%
10% < 20%	0,74%	1,01%	0,09%	0,66%	10% < 20%	0,05%	0,50%	0,09%	0,08%
20% < 30%	0,25%	0,75%	0,18%	0,27%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,25%	0,09%	0,04%
30% < 40%	0,05%	0,50%	0,09%	0,08%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,25%	0,75%	0,46%	0,31%	40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
100%	0,04%	0,00%	0,09%	0,04%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.680	398	1.085	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.666	398	1.099	7.163

Pas d'application (%)					Pas d'application (%)				
Module 5	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 6	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	59,15%	47,24%	72,17%	60,46%	0 %	42,13%	37,44%	42,68%	41,95%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,05%	0,00%	0,09%	0,06%	1% < 2%	6,19%	7,79%	5,46%	6,17%
2% < 5%	16,57%	19,85%	19,45%	17,19%	2% < 5%	49,06%	49,50%	50,68%	49,34%
5% < 10%	8,79%	11,56%	5,99%	8,52%	5% < 10%	2,38%	4,52%	1,18%	2,32%
10% < 20%	10,85%	13,07%	2,21%	9,66%	10% < 20%	0,23%	0,75%	0,22%	0,22%
20% < 30%	4,12%	7,29%	0,09%	3,69%	20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
30% < 40%	0,48%	1,01%	0,00%	0,43%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.680	398	1.085	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.666	398	1.099	7.163

Ne sait pas (%)					Ne sait pas (%)				
Module 7	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 8	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	93,09%	92,48%	91,06%	92,74%	0 %	83,31%	79,32%	82,95%	83,02%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,09%	0,01%	1% < 2%	6,70%	7,54%	5,93%	6,63%
2% < 5%	5,37%	5,34%	7,22%	5,65%	2% < 5%	8,53%	11,44%	9,55%	8,85%
5% < 10%	1,12%	0,97%	1,09%	1,09%	5% < 10%	1,27%	1,70%	1,58%	1,34%
10% < 20%	0,41%	0,97%	0,36%	0,43%	10% < 20%	0,11%	0,00%	0,00%	0,08%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,24%	0,27%	0,06%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	40% < 100%	0,07%	0,00%	0,00%	0,06%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.643	412	1.108	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.673	411	1.079	7.163

Refus (%)					Refus (%)				
Module 7	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 8	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	99,03%	97,82%	99,01%	98,95%	0 %	94,52%	96,59%	94,07%	94,57%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1% < 2%	2,61%	1,70%	2,78%	2,58%
2% < 5%	0,80%	1,70%	0,90%	0,87%	2% < 5%	2,27%	0,73%	2,50%	2,22%
5% < 10%	0,05%	0,49%	0,00%	0,07%	5% < 10%	0,37%	0,49%	0,28%	0,36%
10% < 20%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	10% < 20%	0,09%	0,24%	0,09%	0,10%
20% < 30%	0,05%	0,00%	0,00%	0,04%	20% < 30%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,05%	0,00%	0,09%	0,06%	40% < 100%	0,11%	0,24%	0,19%	0,13%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,09%	0,01%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.643	412	1.108	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.673	411	1.079	7.163

Pas d'application (%)					Pas d'application (%)				
Module 7	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 8	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	0 %	91,43%	92,21%	92,86%	91,69%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1% < 2%	1,89%	0,97%	2,22%	1,88%
2% < 5%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	2% < 5%	4,14%	4,87%	3,80%	4,13%
5% < 10%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	5% < 10%	2,03%	1,70%	0,65%	1,80%
10% < 20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	10% < 20%	0,51%	0,24%	0,46%	0,49%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.643	412	1.108	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.673	411	1.079	7.163

Title of the columns:

- « Pas de tierce p. » = « No third person »
- « Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt » = « Third person(s) present but not the partner »
- « Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt » = « Third person(s) present including at least the partner »

Ne sait pas (%)					Ne sait pas (%)				
Module 9	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 10	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	80,20%	73,00%	84,69%	80,64%	0 %	84,07%	82,54%	92,09%	85,27%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	1% < 2%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
2% < 5%	12,65%	17,72%	11,62%	12,66%	2% < 5%	13,38%	12,97%	6,61%	12,27%
5% < 10%	4,14%	6,75%	3,14%	4,08%	5% < 10%	1,98%	3,24%	0,87%	1,87%
10% < 20%	1,16%	2,11%	0,37%	1,07%	10% < 20%	0,39%	1,00%	0,35%	0,42%
20% < 30%	0,15%	0,00%	0,09%	0,14%	20% < 30%	0,12%	0,25%	0,00%	0,11%
30% < 40%	0,12%	0,42%	0,00%	0,11%	30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,09%	0,03%
40% < 100%	0,27%	0,00%	0,09%	0,24%	40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
100%	1,27%	0,00%	0,00%	1,03%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.842	237	1.084	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.612	401	1.150	7.163
Refus (%)					Refus (%)				
Module 9	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 10	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	95,64%	94,94%	94,83%	95,49%	0 %	92,53%	92,52%	90,26%	92,17%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
2% < 5%	3,08%	3,80%	4,06%	3,25%	2% < 5%	6,11%	6,48%	8,00%	6,44%
5% < 10%	0,41%	0,00%	0,55%	0,42%	5% < 10%	1,03%	0,50%	1,48%	1,07%
10% < 20%	0,03%	0,42%	0,18%	0,07%	10% < 20%	0,25%	0,25%	0,09%	0,22%
20% < 30%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
30% < 40%	0,03%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
40% < 100%	0,09%	0,84%	0,37%	0,15%	40% < 100%	0,04%	0,25%	0,09%	0,06%
100%	0,68%	0,00%	0,00%	0,56%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,09%	0,01%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.842	237	1.084	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.612	401	1.150	7.163
Pas d'application (%)					Pas d'application (%)				
Module 9	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 10	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	99,59%	98,73%	99,35%	99,53%	0 %	18,39%	19,20%	12,70%	17,52%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,09%	0,01%	1% < 2%	0,09%	0,00%	0,00%	0,07%
2% < 5%	0,41%	1,27%	0,55%	0,46%	2% < 5%	32,50%	37,91%	30,43%	32,47%
5% < 10%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	5% < 10%	38,88%	36,91%	41,22%	39,15%
10% < 20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	10% < 20%	10,14%	5,99%	15,65%	10,79%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.842	237	1.084	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.612	401	1.150	7.163
Ne sait pas (%)					Ne sait pas (%)				
Module 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 1 à 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	94,46%	92,27%	92,87%	94,08%	0 %	24,88%	20,95%	32,47%	25,90%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	44,02%	39,15%	42,35%	43,47%
1% < 2%	3,88%	3,74%	4,55%	3,98%	1% < 2%	17,24%	18,95%	16,66%	16,75%
2% < 5%	0,88%	2,74%	1,20%	1,03%	2% < 5%	12,09%	17,46%	10,14%	12,08%
5% < 10%	0,66%	0,25%	0,86%	0,67%	5% < 10%	1,55%	3,24%	1,37%	1,62%
10% < 20%	0,07%	0,75%	0,43%	0,17%	10% < 20%	0,18%	0,25%	0,00%	0,15%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,25%	0,00%	0,01%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,09%	0,03%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163
Refus (%)					Refus (%)				
Module 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 1 à 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	94,21%	93,52%	93,56%	94,07%	0 %	72,31%	68,83%	75,09%	72,46%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	21,78%	22,19%	21,22%	21,71%
1% < 2%	3,36%	3,49%	4,30%	3,52%	1% < 2%	3,27%	4,74%	2,32%	3,20%
2% < 5%	1,29%	1,00%	0,86%	1,20%	2% < 5%	2,05%	5,24%	0,60%	2,00%
5% < 10%	0,88%	1,00%	0,86%	0,88%	5% < 10%	0,32%	0,75%	0,52%	0,38%
10% < 20%	0,18%	0,75%	0,17%	0,21%	10% < 20%	0,23%	0,25%	0,09%	0,21%
20% < 30%	0,05%	0,25%	0,00%	0,06%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,09%	0,03%
30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%	30% < 40%	0,02%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,17%	0,04%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,01%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,09%	0,01%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163
Pas d'application (%)					Pas d'application (%)				
Module 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 1 à 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	0 %	2,80%	1,25%	1,89%	2,57%
0% > < 1%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0% > < 1%	26,24%	28,18%	22,85%	25,80%
1% < 2%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	1% < 2%	32,19%	31,67%	36,34%	32,84%
2% < 5%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	2% < 5%	37,25%	36,16%	38,83%	37,44%
5% < 10%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	5% < 10%	1,52%	2,74%	0,09%	1,35%
10% < 20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	10% < 20%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	20% < 30%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	30% < 40%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	40% < 100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163
NSP + Refus (%)					NSP + Refus (%)				
Module 1 à 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total	Module 1 à 11	Pas de tierce p.	Tierce(s) p. sans le cjt	Tierce(s) p. dont le cjt	Total
0 %	16,21%	16,21%	16,21%	16,21%	0 %	20,28%	27,84%	27,84%	21,28%
0% > < 1%	42,05%	37,41%	41,75%	41,74%	0% > < 1%	42,05%	37,41%	41,75%	41,74%
1% < 2%	19,29%	19,95%	16,32%	18,85%	1% < 2%	19,29%	19,95%	16,32%	18,85%
2% < 5%	14,93%	18,20%	11,60%	14,57%	2% < 5%	14,93%	18,20%	11,60%	14,57%
5% < 10%	2,82%	7,23%	1,98%	2,93%	5% < 10%	2,82%	7,23%	1,98%	2,93%
10% < 20%	0,55%	1,00%	0,26%	0,53%	10% < 20%	0,55%	1,00%	0,26%	0,53%
20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,17%	0,04%	20% < 30%	0,02%	0,00%	0,17%	0,04%
30% < 40%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%	30% < 40%	0,04%	0,00%	0,00%	0,03%
40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,09%	0,03%	40% < 100%	0,02%	0,00%	0,09%	0,03%
100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	100%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	Total	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%	100,00%
Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163	Eff. Tot.	5.598	401	1.164	7.163